

Drexel University

Group 5 Carlsberg Group Final Report

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For this project, teams from Drexel University and the Berlin School of Economics & Law analyzed the DraughtMaster and the feasibility of this system being introduced into the United States. As the DraughtMaster is a plastic keg, we found a few general problems with this innovation. One is that there is a contradiction between plastic and sustainability. When plastic is produced, CO₂ emissions go into the air. Another issue is that the system is very complex and bars and restaurants are used to using an aluminum keg. As these are just a few issues we originally found, we will present a few others we discovered from interviews we conducted.

Each team was tasked with developing interviews to be conducted with consumers of beer and business owners that serve draft beer to gain their perspectives on this innovative technology, and its ability to achieve sustainability. We were able to gather concrete evidence through our interviews which we will present later along with extensive research about the DraughtMaster.

By gathering both information from our interviews, and from Carlsberg, we were able to form a better understanding as to what are some of the key issues with this new innovation. We needed to have a clear understanding of what the DraughtMaster was before going into our interviews so we could clearly explain this process to our interviewees, as well as be able to form our own educated opinion. Conducting interviews allowed our class to get up-to-date information from bar owners and beer-drinking consumers about what their personal experience has been like, and gain their insights about the innovation. Conducting both primary and secondary research allowed us to relate the information we gathered from our interviews back to the information we gathered from first researching the DraughtMaster. From our research, we concluded that it would be feasible to bring the DraughtMaster into the United States. But, we will discuss throughout this paper some suggestions we have for how to approach this as we do have some concerns about the innovation as it currently stands.

For this analysis, Professor Korschun (Drexel) and Professor Klose (Berlin) formed teams with students from Drexel and students from Berlin who collaborated as to how to organize this project. From the two classes, there were a total of 10 teams who completed and worked on the project. Our team consisted of 4 Americans and 3 German students. After establishing our code of conduct and team roles, we started thinking about who we would interview for our B2C interviews and B2B interviews. We conducted both B2C and B2B interviews to get perspectives from both beer-drinking consumers, as well as businesses who serve tap beer and have a keg system. As we are trying to see if this innovation would be feasible in the United States, it made logical sense to conduct interviews to get perspectives from people who actually work with kegs daily, and who would actually be using the DraughtMaster in their businesses.

For our B2C interviews, we decided to interview one person from the United States and one person from Germany. For our first B2C interview, we chose a 61-year-old business consultant from America. We decided to interview him because our teammate knows him well, and knows he loves tap beer, and has a very specific beer he likes. For our second B2C interview, we chose a 26-year-old female Marketing Manager from Berlin, Germany. We wanted to get a

perspective from someone who lives in Germany and also enjoys tap beer. Interviewing someone from the United States and Germany, allowed us to see what similarities and differences there are among beer drinkers in each country, as well as the general consensus about sustainability.

Before having the actual interview our team created discussion guides to organize the flow of our interviews and make sure we were touching on all key points. First off, we created an overall goal for the B2C interview. Our goal was to gauge the interest of beer consumers in terms of introducing a sustainable keg, and how they would respond to this innovation. We then divided our discussion guide into sections: The set-up, Introduction, General Beer Consumption, Bar experience, Introduction of Carlsberg Group Innovation, and Final Decision. Some of the questions we asked were, how do you distinguish the quality of beer? What is your opinion of replacing aluminum kegs with plastic kegs, and what does sustainability mean to you? We also got their overall impression of the Carlsberg keg and if they would recommend this innovation to bar owners.

Our class conducted a total of 10 B2C interviews in the United States and 10 in Germany. After we conducted the interviews, each team was assigned to do a qualitative analysis of another group's B2C interviews. The goal was to gather an in-depth understanding of the participant's perception, reactions, and suggestions about the DraughtMaster system. We looked for similarities and differences among our interviewees in terms of their openness to the innovation and their stance on sustainability. Our analysis allowed us to see that many people had a positive reaction to the idea of a more sustainable keg. About 50% of the participants liked that the plastic kegs are recyclable and more convenient to move around. A 25-year-old female interviewee from Philadelphia stated that it is better than metal kegs and would not mind paying extra for a good beer. However, there are concerns about the difference in taste and quality.

For our group's B2B interview, we interviewed a representative with 7-years of bartending experience. He is the Director of Operations for a bar in the United States named: Casey's Public House in Newtown Square, PA. Our goal through this interview was to gain this representative's perspective on the DraughtMaster technology, given their experience with keg beer, since we were tasked with deciding whether Carlsberg should enter the United States' bars and restaurants with their plastic keg system.

The interview developed by our team was structured into different sections which first included a set-up of the interview where permission was asked to record the conversation for purposes of transferring the audio to a written transcript for analysis. From there, the participant was asked about his background in the bar industry which was needed to qualify his expertise and eventual opinions about the DraughtMaster technology implementation into bars across the United States. After completing the set-up portion of the interview, the representative was asked about details of Casey's Public House business. Questions included from this section are as follows:

- What types of beer do you have on tap?
- Describe the importance of tap beer to Casey's business?
- Can you please describe the process of how your (tap)beer system works?

- Is draft beer more popular than bottles in your bar?
- Can you explain the process of tapping a beer and changing a keg for the bar?

The interviewee was then asked his personal opinions on sustainability and the importance of sustainability to Casey's business. The conversation transitioned to an introduction of the Carlsberg DraughtMaster technology and his opinions of this new system. Example questions from this section are as follows:

- What do you think a more sustainable keg would look like?
- What is your opinion of replacing aluminum kegs with plastic kegs?
- What do you think about this innovation? Likes vs. Dislikes?
- How do you think implementing this keg would affect your business operations?
- What concerns do you have about the Draughtmaster?

The interview concluded with overall impressions and a final decision from the representative where he discussed if he would implement this keg technology into his business.

Our B2B interview described in the prior paragraph totaled 52 minutes in length. The representative provided insight from the front of the house (bartending) and management departments which is important for DraughtMaster and its potential implementation into bars across the United States. Our group was made aware that Casey's Bar located in Newtown Square and Berwyn are family businesses where draft beer is most popular and preferred; each location has 12-20 taps for draft beer. When asked about current issues in the bar industry, the representative stated, "The major struggle is people being able to move the physical keg. It's heavy... Getting the other keg back into a place where the old one was, and moving heavy stuff around is time-consuming...It's kind of just a process that I feel like there could be ways to eliminate that."

After viewing the youtube video description of the DraughtMaster technology, the representative provided the following impression: "The DraughtMaster, definitely a solution in that sense, with the plastic being a lighter material, and a little more portable than the regular keg ... I think it's a great solution. I mean, they're lighter, they're easier to move around. I think that is good. I don't see anything. I'm not opposed to it... The only issue would be that it's smaller than a regular one." It is important for DraughtMaster to highlight its lightweight technology as a solution to current keg technology given the response our representative provided.

After conducting our B2B interviews, our class filled out a B2B analysis excel sheet that focused on a few different aspects like the general background of the interviewee, importance of tap to the business, their customer base, likes/dislikes of DraughtMaster, and if they see a conflict between sustainability and using plastics. Each group analyzed another group's interview, to eventually have 10 interviews filled out in this table. We were able to then compare each interview and gather key findings which we will explain next.

Based on the 2 B2C interviews our team conducted, as well as the rest of the class's interviews, it is concluded that overall sustainability is important to Americans, however, they don't have the resources set in place to be sustainable. Our American interviewee stated that as he is getting older, he doesn't believe that having this sustainable keg would make a difference in

terms of going to a particular bar that has this keg. He emphasized that there needs to be more research done to see how profitable and impactful it would be for a restaurant. Germany happens to be more sustainable but would not invest in this system. Our German interviewee points out that trying to make the beer process sustainable might not be as appealing to consumers, since beer consumers don't think about sustainability. They are more reserved about the idea by questioning the price difference and the desired experience.

After analyzing and reviewing other teams' B2B interviews, there were common themes and concerns for the DraughtMaster that should be highlighted. We got a consensus that bars and restaurants would be less likely to invest in the system, while breweries would be more open to the idea. A bar manager from Munich, Germany expressed that he has concerns about the cost of implementation of this technology in his bar. He assumed that his business would have to replace his current draft system to make way for the DraughtMaster. A general manager from a bar located in Quakertown, PA expressed similar concerns in the following quote from her interview: "Okay, yeah, I know, restaurants would like to know what that cost would be upfront. Because a lot of them don't necessarily have room for a lot of new equipment. Or they have keg rooms that they've already spent all of this money on creating. But that cost specifically to restaurants right now is a little scary, especially if you have to bring in a whole new system." A business owner from Potsdam, Brandenburg, Germany provided the following quote which clarifies for the two prior business owners: "Implementing the DM depends on the brewery and the cost and effort. The owner of the business chose to implement the DM in some breweries because it is more financially feasible, and also it allows him to provide a larger variety of beers on tap. Traditional kegs are more useful for bars where beer is sold in large quantities. They are cheaper per liter and don't have to be replaced as often."

Another key finding is about the recyclability of plastic. A waiter from Germany explained in the interview how he understands that plastic is difficult to recycle, and he prefers the reuse system which works better with metal kegs. Specifically, he stated, "Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends if the plastic is recycled." The interview did express that if Carlsberg can make the plastic keg reusable the same or more times compared to a metal keg, then this innovation might be successful. Another interviewee our class had was a family-owned restaurant in Germany. They had similar doubts about the plastic keg. They were uncertain of how to properly dispose of the plastic kegs when they were finished. They said, "But where does all the plastic go after the keg is empty? The kegs take up a lot of space. Do you have to dispose of them yourself?"

A third key finding and theme from the majority of the B2B interviews addressed concerns with the implementation of the DraughtMaster technology in their respective businesses. While many of the business representatives found the technology and kegs to be innovative and interesting, they were skeptical about the investment needed to install the DraughtMaster technology into their bars. A general manager from a bar in PA highlighted these concerns while stating that restaurants may be open to the idea of the DraughtMaster technology but with businesses now open after their prolonged closure, they are in survival mode and may

not be willing to take on the project of implementation during this busy period. A bartender from Ravensburg, Germany stated “But I don't know if the installation is that easy as promised, I am a bit skeptical and I have to employ the new system.” Of the 10 business representatives interviewed for this project, 6 directly expressed they needed further information about the installation of this technology in their bars.

Our first recommendation would be to target breweries first. Many of the interviewees expressed that this innovation would be better targeted at breweries specifically because of the cost aspect. As many bars and restaurants already have aluminum keg systems and understand how they operate, implementing this new innovation would mean learning a whole new process, training all staff, and an initial high cost for a smaller keg. Breweries can also reuse the plastic kegs and turn them into something else or remake the plastic kegs for future use. Restaurants and bars cannot be focusing on this as they have other operations to be concerned about, and the investment they would be making just solely on tap beer would be a lot. It is also clear that they might not want to do this because it is an entirely new system that they don't know anything about yet which would take a good amount of time to learn. Therefore, we would recommend targeting breweries first as they are the producers of beer and would be more willing to invest in that kind of system.

Our second recommendation would be based on our findings on the problem of recycling plastics. Carlsberg needs to make sure the recycling process is followed through till the end to ensure that the plastic kegs are being recycled properly and efficiently. We recommend providing a thorough plan on how to do so. When looking at the Carlsberg website, there are videos available that mention how to change a flex 20 keg, yet it only says how to change the keg not how to recycle or what to do after the keg is done being used. Specifically, in the flex 20 keg video, it just says “discard”. We believe having a more in-depth explanation of the afterlife of the plastic keg would be beneficial for The Carlsberg Group as they can clearly show what they are doing to make sure this plastic keg is being recycled properly, and how investing in this keg will make a positive impact on the businesses and the planet.

Finally, to address the concerns of implementation, we feel that Carlsberg should include information about the installation process of this technology in its marketing materials and pitches. This could help ease business owners' concerns which will lead to an open-minded approach from businesses when weighing the decision of whether to implement the DraughtMaster into their bars. We also recommend that Carlsberg should include testimonials from current clients that have gone through the implementation process which could provide insights into the process. If Carlsberg finds that education of their implementation process does not help, they could waive the upfront installation costs to help sign-on accounts. This will show they care for their business partners which will create upfront trust in the business relationship. Carlsberg could also help clients install the technology as a courtesy, so that is one less thing the businesses have to worry about.